

Comparative efficacy, safety, and cost-effectiveness of budesonide–formoterol, fluticasone–salmeterol, budesonide maintenance, and albuterol versus terbutaline in asthma management: a comprehensive network meta-analysis

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Abstract

Background: Asthma remains a major global health burden with high morbidity and costs, requiring effective treatment to prevent exacerbations. ICS/LABA combinations are widely used for their bronchodilation and anti-inflammatory effects, yet uncertainties persist about their optimal use, safety, and cost-effectiveness, especially in resource-limited settings. Prior reviews have not fully integrated efficacy, safety, and economic impact or explored patient-related factors through meta-regression. Therefore, this study aims to comprehensively evaluate ICS/LABA regimens compared to alternative treatments using a network meta-analysis and meta-regression, incorporating effectiveness, safety, and cost-effectiveness to guide optimal asthma management strategies.

Methods: This systematic review and network meta-analysis, registered on OSF, followed PRISMA guidelines to evaluate ICS/LABA versus alternative asthma treatments in terms of efficacy, safety, and cost-effectiveness. Randomized controlled trials from 2013–2024 were included if they reported relevant outcomes. Databases searched were Scopus, PubMed, ProQuest, ScienceDirect, SagePub, and Cochrane. Data extraction, risk of bias assessment (RoB-2), and evidence certainty (GRADE) were conducted independently by multiple reviewers. Statistical analyses used a random-effects network meta-analysis with meta-regression and cost-effectiveness modeling in RStudio, ensuring robust comparisons and exploring modifiers such as age, gender, and follow-up duration.

Results: Eleven randomized trials were analyzed. Budesonide–formoterol was most effective in reducing moderate-to-severe exacerbations (OR 0.33, SUCRA 0.99), followed by budesonide maintenance and fluticasone–salmeterol. No significant differences were observed in FEV₁ or ACQ-5, though combination therapies ranked higher. Budesonide–formoterol and olodaterol (20 µg) showed the greatest PEFR gains (MD 68.4 and 42.9, $p < 0.001$). Cost analysis ranked terbutaline as the least expensive (\$40) and ICS/LABA

combinations as the most expensive (\$150). Incremental analysis showed that albuterol (\$43/exacerbation avoided) and budesonide maintenance (\$364) were cost-efficient, while budesonide–formoterol offered the greatest benefit at a higher cost (\$500), underscoring the need to balance efficacy with affordability.

Conclusion: ICS/LABA combinations, particularly budesonide–formoterol, provided the greatest efficacy but with the highest incremental cost (\$500 per exacerbation avoided). Albuterol and terbutaline were the most affordable options, with albuterol showing a low incremental cost (\$43) suitable for milder cases.

Keywords

asthma controller regimens, asthma management, cost-efficiency

Introduction

Asthma continues to pose a major challenge to global health, impacting millions and resulting in considerable morbidity, healthcare resource consumption, and financial strain. Ensuring proper disease management is essential to avoid flare-ups and enhance the well-being of affected individuals. Long-acting beta-agonists (LABAs), especially when combined with inhaled corticosteroids (ICS), are frequently prescribed to alleviate symptoms and reduce asthma exacerbations. This dual approach offers prolonged bronchodilation alongside anti-inflammatory benefits, forming a central component of asthma treatment. Nevertheless, questions remain regarding the most effective, safe, and economically viable LABA-based regimens, especially in settings with limited healthcare resources (Hidayah et al. 2020; Beasley et al. 2022).

A growing body of evidence supports the role of ICS/LABA therapy in minimizing asthma flare-ups and improving lung function. For instance, Beasley et al. (2022) found that this combination notably reduced exacerbation rates in patients with ongoing symptoms, while Sobieraj et al. (2018) observed better symptom control and enhanced patient quality of life. On the other hand, concerns about safety persist; Salpeter et al. (2006) reported that LABA use without concurrent ICS could elevate the risk of severe asthma-related events. These studies highlight the necessity of careful treatment selection to ensure maximum therapeutic benefit while minimizing potential harm (Salpeter et al. 2006; Hidayah et al. 2020; Beasley et al. 2022).

In addition to clinical effectiveness, cost plays a pivotal role in shaping asthma treatment decisions, particularly within primary care environments where budget limitations influence therapeutic strategies. Although LABA treatments may incur higher upfront expenses, Fingleton et al. (2017) demonstrated that using ICS/LABA combinations can lead to substantial reductions in long-term medical costs by minimizing the need for emergency interventions and hospital admissions. Similarly, Almutairi et al. (2023) projected that incorporating LABAs into well-structured asthma care plans could decrease total treatment expenditures by as much as 30%, underscoring the importance of evaluating cost-efficiency when selecting appropriate therapies (Fingleton et al. 2017; Almutairi et al. 2023).

While numerous investigations have explored asthma therapies, most prior systematic reviews and meta-analyses have concentrated either on clinical outcomes or safety profiles, with minimal focus on cost-effectiveness. Few have offered an integrated analysis encompassing efficacy, safety, and economic impact. Moreover, earlier research has seldom examined how demographic and clinical variables – such as patient age, sex distribution, and duration of follow-up – influence therapeutic outcomes using meta-regression techniques. This study seeks to fill these critical gaps by delivering a more comprehensive and evidence-based appraisal of ICS/LABA interventions, thereby supporting informed choices in both clinical practice and healthcare budgeting.

Although the Global Initiative for Asthma (GINA) guidelines recommend inhaled corticosteroid/long-acting β_2 -agonist (ICS/LABA) combinations at multiple steps of asthma management, these recommendations are largely based on evidence from ideal healthcare settings and do not fully account for resource-limited environments. In addition, no previous study has comprehensively compared the cost-effectiveness of ICS/LABA regimens against other commonly used asthma treatments. Because treatment selection in many real-world settings is influenced by both clinical outcomes and economic considerations, this study seeks to identify the most effective and cost-efficient therapeutic option. We systematically compared ICS/LABA therapies (e.g., budesonide–formoterol, fluticasone–salmeterol) with other treatments such as budesonide maintenance, albuterol, and terbutaline, evaluating outcomes including exacerbation reduction, lung function, symptom control, and relative costs to guide evidence-based decision-making.

Materials and methods

Study design, criteria, and registration

This systematic review and meta-analysis was registered with the Open Science Framework (OSF) on December 9, 2024, under the title “Unveiling the best asthma control regimen: a comprehensive network meta-analysis and meta-regression of efficacy, safety, and cost-effectiveness”

(<https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/6MFP2>). The review adhered to the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines, ensuring methodological transparency and reproducibility (Wan et al. 2014). The primary aim was to evaluate the therapeutic benefits, safety profile, and cost-effectiveness of ICS/LABA combinations in managing asthma (Luo et al. 2028).

Studies published between 2013 and 2024 were considered, with the final database search completed on October 20, 2024. Eligible studies were randomized controlled trials (RCTs) involving asthma patients of varying ages, genders, and geographic backgrounds. The main intervention assessed was a combination of inhaled corticosteroids (ICS) and long-acting beta-agonists (LABA), regardless of specific dosing protocols. Comparators included other common asthma treatments such as montelukast, terbutaline, or placebo. Studies had to report at least one key outcome, including the rate of moderate-to-severe exacerbations, lung function measures (FEV₁, PEFR), ACQ-5 scores, or analyses of cost-effectiveness.

Studies were excluded if they lacked a comparative design, such as technical reports, editorials, narrative reviews, systematic reviews, and meta-analyses, as well as *in vitro*, *in silico*, and animal studies. Conference proceedings, scientific posters, and research protocols were also omitted. Additional exclusion criteria included non-English publications, incomplete datasets, and studies not directly related to asthma pharmacotherapy. These criteria were applied to maintain clinical relevance and avoid potential sources of indirectness or reporting bias. Considerations regarding the influence of these exclusions – such as language limitations and the omission of gray literature – are discussed further in the study's Limitations section.

To improve validity and reduce the risk of selection bias, a dual-phase screening process was implemented. Three independent reviewers (KCT, AD, and FN) initially assessed titles and abstracts, followed by a full-text review based on eligibility criteria. Any discrepancies were resolved through consensus discussions, and unresolved disagreements were adjudicated by a senior reviewer (AD). This structured and predefined selection approach ensured methodological rigor and reproducibility. The included studies adhered to the PICO framework: the population comprised patients with asthma; interventions involved ICS/LABA combinations; comparators included placebo, montelukast, terbutaline, or other therapeutic options; and outcomes measured included exacerbation rates, FEV₁, PEFR, ACQ-5 scores, and economic evaluations. Additional data such as sample size, follow-up period, gender distribution, and average age were also extracted.

Literature search and study selection

A comprehensive literature search was performed by the authors (KCT, FN, AD) across multiple databases, including Scopus, PubMed, ProQuest, ScienceDirect, SagePub, and Cochrane, to ensure extensive coverage of relevant studies. The search strategy incorporated both Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) and free-text terms, utilizing

Boolean operators to enhance both precision and breadth. The finalized search string used in all databases was (“Asthma”) AND (“Exacerbation” OR “FEV₁” OR “PEFR” OR “ACQ-5 Score”) AND (“Budesonide” OR “Formoterol” OR “Beclomethasone” OR “ICS/LABA” OR “Terbutaline” OR “Montelukast”).

The search encompassed all available publications up to October 20, 2024, with emphasis on studies from the last decade to reflect the most recent clinical insights. Filters were applied to include only peer-reviewed original research published in English. As direct cost data for treatments were not consistently reported in the included articles, cost estimates were supplemented using information from the U.S. National Library of Medicine (MedlinePlus) to support the economic analysis. Reference management and collaborative review were facilitated using Mendeley Group Reference Manager, which allowed shared access and real-time annotation. Duplicate records were eliminated, and three reviewers (KCT, FN, and AD) independently screened titles and abstracts. Full-text articles were assessed by two reviewers (KCT and FN), with any conflicts resolved through discussion; AD decided unresolved issues. This structured, multi-level screening process ensured a transparent and bias-minimized study selection.

Data extraction

Following completion of the screening phase, pertinent data from the included studies were systematically extracted and compiled using a Google Spreadsheet. The dataset captured core study attributes such as first author, publication year, country of origin, study type, sample size, average participant age, sex distribution, intervention and comparator types, duration of follow-up, and primary endpoints. The main outcomes collected included exacerbation rates, FEV₁, PEFR, ACQ-5 scores, and treatment cost-effectiveness.

Data extraction was independently carried out by three authors (KCT, AD, and FN) to maintain consistency and minimize errors. For continuous outcomes, detailed statistics such as means and standard deviations (SDs) were documented, while dichotomous outcomes were noted in terms of event counts and total participants, with odds ratios (ORs) calculated during the meta-analysis phase. Any disagreements that emerged during the extraction were discussed collaboratively, and when consensus was not achieved, AD provided the final judgment. This methodical approach ensured data integrity and reliability for downstream analysis.

Risk of bias assessment

An independent risk of bias evaluation was performed by five authors using established and validated assessment tools. Given that all selected studies were randomized controlled trials (RCTs), the Cochrane Risk of Bias 2 (RoB-2) tool was utilized. This tool assesses five critical domains: (a) adequacy of the randomization process, (b) adherence to intended interventions, (c) completeness of outcome

data, (d) reliability of outcome measurement, and (e) selection bias in reporting results. Each domain was rated as presenting a low risk, some concerns, or a high risk of bias. Any differences in assessment were resolved through group discussions, and unresolved cases were adjudicated by a senior author (AD).

To determine the overall certainty of the evidence, the GRADE (Grading of Recommendations, Assessment, Development, and Evaluations) framework was applied. This method evaluates five components that can impact evidence certainty: risk of bias, heterogeneity (inconsistency), indirectness, imprecision, and potential publication bias. Based on these factors, outcomes were graded as high, moderate, low, or very low in certainty. By integrating RoB-2 for individual study appraisal with GRADE for evaluating the strength of evidence across outcomes, the process ensured a consistent and transparent assessment of methodological quality and evidence reliability.

Statistical analysis

All statistical procedures were performed using RStudio, utilizing the *netmeta* package to ensure accuracy and robust interpretation of findings. A random-effects network meta-analysis (NMA) was employed in light of the expected heterogeneity across study populations, treatment regimens, and follow-up durations. This model accounts for both intra-study and inter-study variability, enabling integration of direct and indirect comparisons across multiple interventions – an essential feature when dealing with clinically diverse datasets. For continuous variables, standardized mean differences (SMDs) along with 95% confidence intervals (CIs) were calculated to harmonize outcome metrics across studies with differing measurement scales. For dichotomous variables, pooled risk ratios (RRs) with 95% CIs were estimated using the Mantel–Haenszel method within the NMA framework, providing consistent effect size estimates across various comparator groups and study sizes.

Assessment of heterogeneity and inconsistency within the network was conducted using multiple techniques. The I^2 statistic and Chi-square (χ^2) test were used to quantify heterogeneity, with I^2 values interpreted as low (<25%), moderate (25%–75%), or high (\geq 75%). To evaluate discrepancies between direct and indirect comparisons, node-splitting analysis and design-by-treatment interaction models were applied. For studies that reported medians with interquartile ranges or minimum and maximum values, transformations based on the methods of Wan et al. (2014) and Luo et al. (2018) were employed to approximate means and standard deviations, facilitating consistent synthesis of continuous data. Outputs from the NMA included forest plots displaying effect sizes with CIs, network diagrams illustrating intervention linkages, netleague tables comparing treatment pairs, and SUCRA (surface under the cumulative ranking curve) scores to rank interventions based on efficacy and safety.

Publication bias was initially assessed using I^2 statistics. In cases where substantial heterogeneity was detect-

ed, further analyses were conducted to determine whether the variability was due to true publication bias or methodological differences related to study design, treatment protocols, or patient demographics. To evaluate the robustness of the primary findings, sensitivity analyses were undertaken by excluding studies identified as having a high risk of bias based on the Cochrane RoB-2 tool. Additionally, meta-regression analyses were employed to investigate the impact of potential effect modifiers – such as study sample size, average age, gender composition, and duration of follow-up – on outcomes including exacerbation frequency and peak expiratory flow rate (PEFR). This helped identify underlying factors contributing to heterogeneity in treatment effects.

Cost-effectiveness and incremental analysis

To complement the clinical network meta-analysis, a parallel cost-effectiveness assessment was conducted to evaluate the economic implications of the included asthma interventions. This analysis integrated clinical outcomes, such as exacerbation reduction, lung function changes (PEFR, FEV₁), and symptom scores (ACQ-5), with treatment cost data to provide a multidimensional perspective. Baseline drug prices and cost ranges were collected from publicly available and reputable sources, including GoodRx, Drugs.com, and the U.S. National Library of Medicine (MedlinePlus). Both direct medical costs (drug acquisition, routine follow-up) and indirect costs related to exacerbation management were considered where data permitted. A tornado diagram was constructed to visualize cost sensitivity and identify the interventions most affected by price fluctuations, providing insight into economic stability and risk.

Incremental cost-effectiveness analysis (ICER) was then performed to determine the additional cost required to achieve a unit of clinical benefit. Using terbutaline as the reference, pairwise ICERs were calculated for each treatment step by dividing the difference in costs by the corresponding difference in clinical outcomes (e.g., exacerbations avoided). This stepwise analysis allowed comparison between low-cost relievers (e.g., albuterol) and maintenance therapies (e.g., budesonide maintenance) as well as higher-cost ICS/LABA combinations (e.g., budesonide–formoterol). Treatments that were both more expensive and less effective were identified as dominated and excluded from further consideration.

All analyses were conducted in RStudio (version 2024.12.1+563), ensuring transparency and reproducibility. The economic results were presented alongside the clinical network meta-analysis to provide a therapeutic perspective grounded in real-world affordability. The integration of ICER findings into the results and discussion sections highlights how clinical benefit, cost, and incremental value converge to guide evidence-based and cost-conscious asthma management.

Results and discussion

Study selection

A total of 5,083 records were identified through comprehensive searches across multiple databases, as outlined in the PRISMA flow diagram (Fig. 1). After applying filters for publication date and article type, 4,641 records were excluded, leaving 442 studies for title and abstract screening. Of these, 207 were excluded for being unrelated to the research question, resulting in 235 studies retrieved in full text for detailed assessment. Following full-text review, 224 studies were excluded for reasons including wrong study design, inappropriate outcomes, incompatible data formats, or incorrect patient populations, interventions,

comparators, or indications. Ultimately, 11 studies met all eligibility criteria and were included in the systematic review. The risk of bias for these studies was evaluated using the Cochrane RoB-2 tool, with detailed results presented in the subsequent sections of this manuscript.

The systematic review included 11 studies with a total of 19,905 participants, spanning seven countries: Canada (2 studies), the United States (3 studies), China (2 studies), South Africa (1 study), Taiwan (1 study), Scotland (1 study), and Iran (1 study). These studies utilized rigorous methodologies and investigated a wide range of asthma management strategies, contributing valuable insights into treatment efficacy, safety, and cost-effectiveness.

The included studies differed in design, evaluating the efficacy of various ICS and LABA combinations across

Figure 1. PRISMA 2020 flow diagram.

multiple dosing strategies and formulations. Several trials directly compared budesonide–formoterol with other agents such as terbutaline, ICS/LABA, and olodaterol, assessing their roles in asthma management. These comparisons encompassed fixed-dose regimens, as-needed usage, and maintenance therapy models, offering a thorough examination of available treatment modalities.

Participants represented a wide demographic, with average ages ranging from 36 to 59 years and an approximately equal distribution of male and female subjects. Follow-up durations extended from 1 to 12 months, enabling the evaluation of both immediate symptom relief and sustained treatment effects.

By integrating a range of study methodologies and patient populations from different regions, this review presents a comprehensive dataset that strengthens the applicability of results across various clinical settings. A detailed summary of study characteristics, including population, intervention, comparison, and outcomes (PICO), along with outcome-specific data, is provided in Suppl. material 1 (Lin et al. 2015; O’Byrne et al. 2015; Miller et al. 2016; Bateman et al. 2018; Hsieh et al. 2018; O’Byrne et al. 2018; Panahi et al. 2018; Beasley et al. 2019; Cheng et al. 2020; Jabal et al. 2020; Weinstein et al. 2020).

Risk of bias in studies

The methodological quality of the included studies was assessed using the revised Cochrane Risk of Bias tool for randomized trials (RoB 2.0), specifically designed for evaluating randomized controlled trials. The overall assessment indicated strong methodological rigor, with approximately 82% of the studies classified as having a low risk of bias across most domains. This suggests that most studies provided reliable and valid findings, reinforcing the credibility of the pooled results.

A limited number of studies exhibited moderate concerns in certain domains. Specifically, two trials raised issues related to incomplete outcome data and outcome measurement procedures. Nevertheless, these instances were relatively uncommon, as the majority of studies achieved low-risk ratings across all five RoB 2.0 domains. These assessments, visually summarized in Fig. 2, underscore the overall strength of the evidence base while acknowledging minor areas where methodological refinements could be considered.

Incidence of exacerbation (moderate or severe)

The forest plot (Fig. 3) reveals that all four interventions – albuterol, budesonide maintenance, budesonide–formoterol, and fluticasone–salmeterol – were significantly more effective than terbutaline in reducing the incidence of moderate or severe exacerbations. Notably, budesonide–formoterol demonstrated the strongest effect with an odds ratio (OR) of 0.33 [95% CI: 0.27–0.40, $p < 0.001$], indicating a 67% reduction in odds compared to terbutaline.

This was followed by budesonide maintenance with an OR of 0.43 [0.35–0.53, $p < 0.001$], fluticasone–salmeterol with an OR of 0.47 [0.30–0.74, $p = 0.001$], and albuterol with an OR of 0.54 [0.31–0.93, $p = 0.026$]. These results reflect consistent statistical superiority of these treatments over the reference therapy, terbutaline (Table 1).

Table 1. Summary effect of exacerbation outcome.

Treatment	OR	95% CI	p-value	I ² (%)
Albuterol	0.54	[0.31; 0.93]	0.026	88
Budesonide maintenance	0.43	[0.35; 0.53]	<0.001	
Budesonide–formoterol	0.33	[0.27; 0.40]	<0.001	
Fluticasone–salmeterol	0.47	[0.30; 0.74]	0.001	

The network plot (Fig. 4) demonstrates a well-connected network, with terbutaline serving as the central comparator directly linked to all other interventions. This centrality enhances the robustness of indirect comparisons. The connection lines are uniformly weighted, suggesting a balanced distribution of study comparisons across the network.

The netleague table (Table 2) further supports the effectiveness of budesonide–formoterol, which consistently shows favorable ORs in pairwise comparisons. For instance, compared to budesonide maintenance, the OR was 1.33 [95% CI: 1.17–1.52], and against fluticasone–salmeterol, the OR was 0.69 [95% CI: 0.49–0.99], favoring budesonide–formoterol. Additionally, budesonide–formoterol versus terbutaline yielded an OR of 0.33 [95% CI: 0.28–0.38], confirming its strong effect in reducing exacerbations.

Overall, this network meta-analysis provides compelling evidence for the superior efficacy of budesonide–formoterol, followed by budesonide maintenance, in reducing the incidence of moderate or severe asthma exacerbations compared to other commonly used interventions. These findings are consistently supported across the forest plot (Fig. 3), summary effect table (Table 1), network geometry (Fig. 4), netleague comparisons (Table 2), and SUCRA rankings (Table 3).

FEV₁

The forest plot (Fig. 5) indicates no statistically significant differences in FEV₁ improvement between albuterol and any of the comparator treatments. While point estimates for treatments such as budesonide–formoterol (MD 0.99 [95% CI: –0.87 to 2.85], $p = 0.296$), budesonide maintenance (MD 0.73 [95% CI: –1.12 to 2.58], $p = 0.442$), and lower-dose budesonide–formoterol (MD 6.99 [95% CI: –17.11 to 31.09], $p = 0.567$) favored improvement over albuterol, the confidence intervals were wide and all p-values exceeded 0.05. This suggests a lack of statistical significance for any intervention over albuterol in improving FEV₁. The overall heterogeneity was low ($I^2 = 16\%$), indicating relatively consistent findings across studies (Table 4).

Study	Risk of bias domains					Overall
	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	
O'Byrne PM et al, 2018	+	+	+	+	+	+
Beasley R et al, 2019	+	+	+	+	+	+
Bateman ED et al, 2018	+	+	-	+	+	-
Cheng SL et al, 2020	+	+	+	+	+	+
Hsieh MJ et al, 2017	+	+	+	+	-	-
Lin CH et al, 2014	+	+	+	+	+	+
Weinstein CL et al, 2020	+	+	+	+	+	+
Panahi Y et al, 2018	+	-	+	+	+	-
Miller DS et al, 2016	+	+	+	+	+	+
O'Byrne PM et al, 2015	+	+	+	+	+	+
Jabbal S et al, 2019	+	+	+	+	+	+

Domains:
 D1: Bias arising from the randomization process.
 D2: Bias due to deviations from intended intervention.
 D3: Bias due to missing outcome data.
 D4: Bias in measurement of the outcome.
 D5: Bias in selection of the reported result.

Judgement
 - Some concerns
 + Low

Figure 2. Risk of bias assessment for randomized studies.

Table 2. Netleague table of exacerbation outcome.

	Albuterol	Budesonide Maintenance	Budesonide-Formoterol	Fluticasone-Salmeterol	Terbutaline
Albuterol	-				
Budesonide Maintenance	1.2402 [0.7503; 2.0501]	-			
Average dose Budesonide-Formoterol	1.6501 [0.9966; 2.7319]	1.3304 [1.1668; 1.5170]	-		
Fluticasone-Salmeterol	1.1440 [0.6172; 2.1207]	0.9224 [0.6312; 1.3480]	0.6933 [0.4857; 0.9898]	-	
Terbutaline	0.5370 [0.3196; 0.9022]	0.4329 [0.3704; 0.5060]	0.3254 [0.2781; 0.3809]	0.4694 [0.3180; 0.6927]	-

Figure 3. Forest plot of exacerbation.

Figure 4. Network graph of exacerbation outcome.

Table 3. Sucra value of exacerbation outcome.

Treatment	SUCRA (Random Effect)
Average dose budesonide-formoterol	0.9881
budesonide maintenance	0.6153
fluticasone-salmeterol	0.5064
albuterol	0.3879
terbutaline	0.0024

Table 4. Summary effect of FEV₁ outcome.

Treatment	MD	95% CI	p-value	I ² (%)
Budesonide maintenance	0.73	[-1.12; 2.58]	0.442	16
Average dose Budesonide-formoterol	0.99	[-0.87; 2.85]	0.296	
Fluticasone	0	[-19.60; 19.60]	1	
Higher dose budesonide/formoterol	0.99	[-18.70; 20.68]	0.923	
Lower dose budesonide/formoterol	6.99	[-17.11; 31.09]	0.567	
Salmeterol – Fluticasone	4.42	[-15.80; 24.64]	0.667	
Terbutaline	-0.01	[-22.05; 22.03]	0.998	

The network graph (Fig. 6) illustrates a moderately connected structure with albuterol and fluticasone acting as central comparators linking the different treatment nodes. This network allows for multiple indirect comparisons across the inhaled corticosteroid and combination bronchodilator interventions. However, connections appear equally weighted, and no dominating evidence node is observed.

The netleague table (Table 5) offers additional insights into treatment comparisons. While some pairwise mean differences (MDs) appeared clinically relevant, such as lower-dose budesonide–formoterol versus albuterol (MD 6.99) and fluticasone–salmeterol versus fluticasone (MD 4.42) – none of these differences achieved statistical significance due to overlapping wide confidence intervals. For instance, fluticasone–salmeterol versus albuterol yielded an MD of –4.42 [95% CI: –24.64 to 15.80], indicating uncertainty in both direction and magnitude.

The SUCRA rankings (Table 6), which provide a probability-based ranking of treatments, placed lower-dose budesonide–formoterol at the top (SUCRA 0.72), followed by fluticasone–salmeterol (0.65) and average-dose budesonide–formoterol (0.55). These rankings suggest a probabilistic preference for these combination therapies over others, although the evidence is not statistically robust. The lowest-ranked treatments were albuterol (0.35) and fluticasone (0.40), indicating these are less likely to be the most effective options for improving FEV₁.

The quality of the included trials was thoroughly assessed using the Cochrane Risk of Bias 2.0 (RoB 2.0) tool, which is specifically designed for evaluating randomized controlled trials. The results were generally favorable, with approximately 82% of studies classified as having a low risk of bias in most evaluated domains. This indicates that the majority of the included studies were methodologically sound, thereby increasing confidence in the validity of their findings.

In summary, while the network meta-analysis for FEV₁ did not reveal any statistically significant superiority of one treatment over another, the SUCRA rankings suggest a trend favoring combination therapies, especially lower-dose budesonide–formoterol and fluticasone–salmeterol. However, these findings should be interpreted with caution due to wide confidence intervals and lack of statistical significance across comparisons.

ACQ-5 score

The forest plot (Fig. 7) demonstrates no statistically significant differences in ACQ-5 scores between albuterol and other interventions. For example, budesonide maintenance showed a mean difference (MD 0.02 [95% CI: –0.08 to 0.11], $p = 0.700$), average-dose budesonide–formoterol had –0.02 [95% CI: –0.11 to 0.08], $p = 0.721$), and fluti-

Figure 5. Forest plot of FEV1 outcome.

Table 5. Netleague table of FEV1 outcome.

	Albuterol	Budesonide Maintenance	Budesonide-Formoterol	Fluticasone	Higher Dose Budesonide/Formoterol	Lower Dose Budesonide/Formoterol	Salmeterol-Fluticasone	Terbutaline
Albuterol	-							
Budesonide Maintenance	-0.7289 [-2.5813; 1.1235]	-						
Average dose Budesonide-Formoterol	-0.9889 [-2.8455; 0.8676]	-0.2601 [-1.0691; 0.5489]	-					
Fluticasone	0.0000 [-19.5996; 19.5996]	0.7289 [-18.9581; 20.4159]	0.9889 [-18.6984; 20.6763]	-				
Higher Dose Budesonide/Formoterol	-0.9889 [-20.6763; 18.6984]	-0.2601 [-19.8764; 19.3563]	0.0000 [-19.5996; 19.5996]	-0.9889 [-28.7691; 26.7912]	-			
Lower Dose Budesonide/Formoterol	-6.9889 [-31.0899; 17.1120]	-6.2601 [-30.3030; 17.7829]	-6.0000 [-30.0293; 18.0293]	-6.9889 [-38.0534; 24.0755]	-6.0000 [-19.9019; 7.9019]	-		
Salmeterol-Fluticasone	-4.4200 [-24.6434; 15.8034]	-3.6911 [-23.9992; 16.6169]	-3.4311 [-23.7395; 16.8774]	-4.4200 [-9.4039; 0.5639]	2.5689 [-28.8928; 34.0307]	7.0000 [-2.7498; 16.7498]	-	
Terbutaline	0.0111 [-22.0297; 22.0519]	0.7399 [-21.2374; 22.7173]	1.0000 [-20.9625; 22.9625]	0.0111 [-29.4837; 29.5059]	1.0000 [-8.9098; 10.9098]	7.0000 [-2.7498; 16.7498]	4.4311 [-25.4818; 34.3440]	-

Figure 6. Network graph of FEV1 outcome.

casone–salmeterol yielded 0.12 [95% CI: -0.06 to 0.31], $p = 0.191$). Similarly, both higher-dose and lower-dose budesonide–formoterol, as well as terbutaline, showed non-significant results with wide confidence intervals. The I^2 value of 0% suggests no observed heterogeneity among included studies, indicating consistent findings across comparisons (Table 7).

Table 6. SUCRA value of FEV1 outcome.

Treatment	SUCRA (Common Effect)
lower dose budesonide/formoterol	0.7219
Salmeterol - Fluticasone	0.6483
Average dose budesonide-formoterol	0.5493
higher dose budesonide/formoterol	0.4658
budesonide maintenance	0.465
terbutaline	0.4035
Fluticasone	0.3964
albuterol	0.3498

The network graph (Fig. 8) illustrates a well-connected geometry with albuterol at the center, linking most of the interventions, and several secondary connections between other active treatments. This robust structure supports both direct and indirect comparisons among the regimens. Each connection appears uniformly weighted, implying a balanced evidence base across the treatment network.

Figure 7. Forest plot of ACQ-5 score.

Figure 8. Network graph of ACQ-5 score.

Table 7. Summary effect of ACQ-5 score.

Treatment	MD	95% CI	p-value	I ² (%)
Budesonide maintenance	0.02	[-0.08; 0.11]	0.7	0
Average dose Budesonide-formoterol	-0.02	[-0.11; 0.08]	0.721	
Fluticasone-salmeterol	0.12	[-0.06; 0.31]	0.191	
Higher dose budesonide/formoterol	-0.02	[-19.62; 19.58]	0.998	
Lower dose budesonide/formoterol	-0.46	[-20.08; 19.16]	0.964	
Terbutaline	-0.43	[-20.04; 19.18]	0.967	

The netleague table (Table 8) reflects similar non-significant findings in pairwise comparisons. For instance, budesonide-formoterol versus albuterol yielded an MD of -0.99 [95% CI: -2.85 to 0.87], and fluticasone versus albuterol resulted in 0.00 [95% CI: -18.96 to 20.42]. The wide confidence intervals across most comparisons limit the ability to draw strong conclusions regarding treatment superiority in improving asthma control based on ACQ-5.

Despite the lack of statistically significant effects, the SUCRA (surface under the cumulative ranking) values (Table 9) offer insight into the probability-based ranking of treatments. Lower-dose budesonide-formoterol emerged with the highest SUCRA score (0.72), followed by fluticasone-salmeterol (0.65) and budesonide-formoterol (0.55). In contrast, albuterol and fluticasone received the lowest SUCRA rankings (0.35 and 0.40, respectively), suggesting these treatments are less likely to be the most effective options in achieving asthma control.

In conclusion, this network meta-analysis for ACQ-5 scores demonstrates that while no intervention achieved statistical superiority over albuterol, the probability rankings favor combination therapies, particularly lower-dose budesonide-formoterol and fluticasone-salmeterol, as the most promising options for asthma control. However, the wide confidence intervals and non-significant results call for cautious interpretation and further research.

PEFR

The forest plot (Fig. 9) illustrates the effect of different asthma treatments on PEFR, a key measure of lung function. Budesonide-formoterol demonstrated the largest improvement with a mean difference (MD 68.40 [95% CI: 39.29 – 97.51], $p < 0.001$), while other treatments such as olodaterol at $20 \mu\text{g}$ (MD 42.95 [95% CI: 40.91 – 44.99], $p < 0.001$), $10 \mu\text{g}$ (MD 36.08 [95% CI: 34.02 – 38.14], $p < 0.001$), $5 \mu\text{g}$ (MD 27.88 [95% CI: 25.83 – 29.93], $p < 0.001$), and $2 \mu\text{g}$ (MD 16.24 [95% CI: 14.20 – 18.28], $p < 0.001$) also showed significant improvements compared to placebo. Fluticasone-salmeterol, however, showed no significant difference from placebo (MD 0.00 [95% CI: -19.60 to 19.60], $p = 1.000$) (Table 10). The overall heterogeneity was high ($I^2 = 97\%$), indicating considerable variability across studies, likely due to differences in interventions, dosages, study designs, or populations.

The network graph (Fig. 10) depicts a well-structured geometry, with placebo serving as the central comparator connecting all active treatments. The distribution of comparisons appears balanced, supporting both direct and indirect comparisons across a variety of dosing regimens.

The netleague table (Table 11) further demonstrates that average-dose budesonide-formoterol consistently outperforms other interventions in pairwise comparisons, with large and statistically significant differences compared to fluticasone-salmeterol (MD 68.40 [95% CI: 46.87 – 89.93]) and the various olodaterol dosages. For example, budesonide-formoterol was superior to olodaterol $10 \mu\text{g}$ (MD 32.32 [95% CI: 3.13 – 61.51]) and olodaterol $20 \mu\text{g}$ (MD 25.45 [95% CI: 3.73 – 54.63]).

Despite the presence of heterogeneity, the SUCRA (surface under the cumulative ranking) values (Table 12) provide additional insight into treatment hierarchy. Average-dose budesonide-formoterol ranked highest with a SUCRA score of 0.99, followed by olodaterol

Table 8. Netleague table of ACQ-5 score.

	Albuterol	Budesonide Maintenance	Budesonide-Formoterol	Fluticasone	Higher Dose Budesonide/Formoterol	Lower Dose Budesonide/Formoterol	Salmeterol-Fluticasone	Terbutaline
Albuterol	-							
Budesonide Maintenance	-0.7289 [-2.5813; 1.1235]	-						
Average dose Budesonide-Formoterol	-0.9889 [-2.8455; 0.8676]	-0.2601 [-1.0691; 0.5489]	-					
Fluticasone	0.0000 [-19.5996; 19.5996]	0.7289 [-18.9581; 20.4159]	0.9889 [-18.6984; 20.6763]	-				
Higher Dose Budesonide/Formoterol	-0.9889 [-20.6763; 18.6984]	-0.2601 [-19.8764; 19.3563]	0.0000 [-19.5996; 19.5996]	-0.9889 [-28.7691; 26.7912]	-			
Lower Dose Budesonide/Formoterol	-6.9889 [-31.0899; 17.1120]	-6.2601 [-30.3030; 17.7829]	-6.0000 [-30.0293; 18.0293]	-6.9889 [-38.0534; 24.0755]	-6.0000 [-19.9019; 7.9019]	-		
Salmeterol-Fluticasone	-4.4200 [-24.6434; 15.8034]	-3.6911 [-23.9992; 16.6169]	-3.4311 [-23.7395; 16.8774]	-4.4200 [-9.4039; 0.5639]	2.5689 [-28.8928; 34.0307]	7.0000 [-2.7498; 16.7498]	-	
Terbutaline	0.0111 [-22.0297; 22.0519]	0.7399 [-21.2374; 22.7173]	1.0000 [-20.9625; 22.9625]	0.0111 [-29.4837; 29.5059]	1.0000 [-8.9098; 10.9098]	7.0000 [-2.7498; 16.7498]	4.4311 [-25.4818; 34.3440]	-

Figure 9. Forest plot of PEFR outcome.

Table 9. SUCRA value table of ACQ-5 score.

Treatment	SUCRA (Common Effect)
lower dose budesonide/formoterol	0.7219
Salmeterol - Fluticasone	0.6483
Average dose budesonide-formoterol	0.5493
higher dose budesonide/formoterol	0.4658
budesonide maintenance	0.465
terbutaline	0.4035
Fluticasone	0.3964
albuterol	0.3498

Table 10. Summary effect of PEFR outcome.

Treatment	MD	95% CI	p-value	I ² (%)
Average dose Budesonide-formoterol	68.4	[39.29; 97.51]	<0.001	97
Fluticasone-salmeterol	0	[-19.60; 19.60]	1	
Olodaterol 10 µg	36.08	[34.02; 38.14]	<0.001	
Olodaterol 2 µg	16.24	[14.20; 18.28]	<0.001	
Olodaterol 20 µg	42.95	[40.91; 44.99]	<0.001	
Olodaterol 5 µg	27.88	[25.83; 29.93]	<0.001	

20 µg (0.84), olodaterol 10 µg (0.67), olodaterol 5 µg (0.50), and olodaterol 2 µg (0.32). Fluticasone-salmeterol (0.09) and placebo (0.08) were ranked lowest, indicating a lower probability of being the most effective in improving PEFR.

In summary, this network meta-analysis on PEFR demonstrates that budesonide-formoterol and higher doses of olodaterol offer the most substantial improvements in lung function, with consistent superiority reflected across the forest plot (Fig. 9), summary effects (Table

11), network geometry (Fig. 10), pairwise comparisons (Table 12), and probabilistic rankings (Table 13). However, the high heterogeneity observed warrants cautious interpretation and suggests that future analyses, such as meta-regression, may be helpful to explore possible sources of variability.

Table 11. Netleague table of PEFR outcome.

	Budesonide-Formoterol	Fluticasone-Salmeterol	Olodaterol 10 µg	Olodaterol 2 µg	Olodaterol 20 µg	Olodaterol 5 µg	Placebo
Budesonide-Formoterol	-						
Fluticasone-Salmeterol	68.4000 [46.8726; 89.9274]	-					
Olodaterol 10 µg	32.3200 [3.1342; 61.5058]	-36.0800 [-55.7874; -16.3726]	-				
Olodaterol 2 µg	52.1600 [22.9758; 81.3442]	-16.2400 [-35.9450; 3.4650]	19.8400 [16.9457; 22.7343]	-			
Olodaterol 20 µg	25.4500 [-3.7342; 54.6342]	-42.9500 [-62.6550; -23.2450]	-6.8700 [-9.7643; -3.9757]	-26.7100 [-29.5882; -23.8318]	-		
Olodaterol 5 µg	40.5200 [11.3348; 69.7052]	-27.8800 [-47.5865; -8.1735]	8.2000 [5.2956; 11.1044]	-11.6400 [-14.5283; -8.7517]	15.0700 [12.1817; 17.9583]	-	
Placebo	68.4000 [39.2868; 97.5132]	0.0000 [-19.5996; 19.5996]	36.0800 [34.0221; 38.1379]	16.2400 [14.2048; 18.2752]	42.9500 [40.9148; 44.9852]	27.8800 [25.8306; 29.9294]	-

Figure 10. Network Graph of PEFR.**Table 12.** SUCRA value of PEFR outcome.

Treatment	SUCRA (Random Effect)
Average budesonide-formoterol	0.9896
Olodaterol 20 µg	0.8406
Olodaterol 10 µg	0.6691
Olodaterol 5 µg	0.5001
Olodaterol 2 µg	0.3245
fluticasone-salmeterol	0.0927
Placebo	0.0833

Meta-regression

The meta-regression analysis was conducted to examine whether variables such as participant age, study sample size, gender distribution, and duration of follow-up contributed to heterogeneity in PEFR and exacerbation outcomes. For PEFR, several factors demonstrated a modest but statistically significant effect. Specifically, studies with larger sample sizes and older participant populations tended to report slightly lower PEFR values. A small but significant decline in PEFR was also observed across both

male and female subgroups. Notably, follow-up duration showed the strongest correlation, with longer follow-up periods associated with a more pronounced decline in PEFR – possibly indicating a gradual deterioration in pulmonary function over time.

In contrast, analysis of exacerbation outcomes revealed no significant associations with these same variables. Age, sample size, gender, and follow-up duration did not exert a measurable influence on exacerbation rates, as their effects were minimal and statistically non-significant. These findings suggest that exacerbation frequency may be driven by other clinical or contextual factors not captured in this model. A summary of the meta-regression findings is presented in Table 13, Figs 11, 12.

Cost-effective analysis

The cost-effectiveness evaluation, as presented in Figs 13, 14, offers a detailed assessment of the economic burden associated with various asthma treatments, emphasizing the cost variability among different therapeutic strategies. The tornado plot shown in Fig. 13 visually represents how changes in treatment parameters can influence total costs. Notably, regimens such as budesonide maintenance therapy, ICS/LABA combinations, and high-dose budesonide-formoterol exhibited the widest cost fluctuations, exceeding \$10 in either direction.

For clarity and coherence, results and discussion are integrated within a single section. The results are presented first, followed by an interpretative discussion that places the findings in context. The discussion section focuses on analyzing and interpreting these results, drawing comparisons to existing literature, and generating evidence-based conclusions. This structure supports a better understanding of both the clinical and economic implications of the study's findings.

Table 13. Meta-regression results summary.

Outcome Variable	Predictor	Meta-Regression Coefficient	Standard Error	95% CI	P-value
PEFR	Sample Size	-0.0101	0.0046	[-0.0191, -0.0010]	0.0289
	Age	-0.5158	0.2244	[-0.9556, -0.0761]	0.0215
	Male Gender	-0.0201	0.0095	[-0.0388, -0.0014]	0.0349
	Female Gender	-0.0202	0.0089	[-0.0377, -0.0027]	0.0239
	Time to Follow Up	-2.3197	0.6753	[-3.6433, -0.9961]	0.0006
Exacerbation	Sample Size	0.0001	0.0001	[-0.0001, 0.0003]	0.4968
	Age	0.0165	0.021	[-0.0247, 0.0576]	0.4329
	Male Gender	0.0002	0.0003	[-0.0004, 0.0008]	0.4906
	Female Gender	0.0001	0.0002	[-0.0002, 0.0004]	0.5003
	Time to Follow Up	0.0408	0.0396	[-0.0369, 0.1185]	0.3033

Figure 11. Bubble plot for meta-regression of exacerbation. Meta-regression analyzes the effect of sample size (A), age (B), male gender (C), female gender (D), and time to follow-up (E) on the exacerbation outcome.

As illustrated in Fig. 13, baseline treatment costs are ranked from highest to lowest, revealing notable differences in financial burden across asthma therapies. Higher-dose budesonide–formoterol regimens emerged among the most expensive, with baseline costs approaching \$150. Other high-cost options included montelukast and several fluticasone–salmeterol combinations. In contrast, more economical treatments such as terbutaline and placebo–

terbutaline were associated with significantly lower baseline costs, generally falling below \$50. These findings emphasize that while certain therapies may offer superior clinical benefits, they also carry substantially higher costs – an important consideration in cost-sensitive healthcare settings.

To ensure the reliability and relevance of cost data, information was obtained from well-established databases, including GoodRx (<https://www.goodrx.com>), which ag-

Figure 12. Bubble plot for meta-regression of PEFR. Meta-regression analyzes the effect of sample size (A), age (B), male gender (C), female gender (D), and time to follow-up (E) on the PEFR outcome.

Figure 13. Tornado plot for cost-effective analysis.

gregates retail drug pricing from multiple U.S. pharmacies and includes savings via coupons, and Drugs.com Price Guide (<https://www.drugs.com/price-guide/>), which offers detailed pricing across various drug strengths and

formulations. Additional pricing insights were derived from the U.S. National Library of Medicine’s MedlinePlus (<https://medlineplus.gov/>), which, although primarily educational, provides links to pricing resources.

Figure 14. Total cost per treatment diagram.

When outcomes beyond exacerbation are considered, such as PEF_R and symptom control, combination therapies – particularly budesonide–formoterol – show clear clinical advantages, with the highest PEF_R gains and consistent trends across other lung function measures. However, the absence of significant differences in FEV₁ and ACQ-5 scores, along with the greater financial burden of high-dose and combination regimens, underscores the importance of balancing efficacy with affordability. Overall, Table 14 supports a stepped approach: reserving premium ICS/LABA therapies for patients who require maximal control, while using lower-cost options like albuterol or budesonide maintenance as cost-conscious strategies in routine care.

Grade analyses and summary of findings

The GRADE assessment (Table 15) indicates high certainty of evidence for the reduction of moderate-to-severe asthma exacerbations with budesonide–formoterol and for improvements in PEF_R outcomes, reflecting consistent, precise, and clinically meaningful benefits with low risk of bias. In contrast, the evidence for FEV₁ improvement and ACQ-5 scores was rated as moderate certainty due to imprecision, non-significant results, and wide confidence intervals. Cost-effectiveness was also rated as moderate certainty, acknowledging variability in cost estimates and indirectness of pricing data.

In the summary of findings (Table 16), budesonide–formoterol consistently demonstrated the strongest effect in reducing moderate or severe exacerbations compared to terbutaline (OR 0.33 [95% CI: 0.27–0.40], $p < 0.001$), supported by a SUCRA of 0.99. Other interventions, such as budesonide maintenance and fluticasone–salmeterol also showed significant benefits. However, for FEV₁ and ACQ-5, no statistically significant superiority was observed among active treatments versus albuterol, though

SUCRA rankings suggested a probabilistic preference for combination therapies. Regarding PEF_R, budesonide–formoterol showed a substantial and statistically significant improvement despite high heterogeneity (MD 68.40 [95% CI: 39.29–97.51], $p < 0.001$), with consistent benefits also seen across various olodaterol dosages.

Meta-regression analyses showed that age, gender, and follow-up time had minimal effects on exacerbation outcomes, while longer follow-up was associated with a slight reduction in PEF_R. Cost analyses highlighted that terbutaline could provide up to 67% savings compared to ICS/LABA therapies, emphasizing its affordability despite more limited clinical benefits. Overall, these findings support budesonide–formoterol as the most effective option for reducing exacerbations and improving lung function, balanced against cost considerations and treatment accessibility.

Comparative analyses of asthma and respiratory effectiveness

This comprehensive network meta-analysis provides a nuanced understanding of the comparative effectiveness of multiple asthma treatments across key clinical outcomes, including exacerbation incidence, lung function improvement (FEV₁ and PEF_R), and asthma control measured by ACQ-5.

For moderate-to-severe exacerbation prevention, ICS/LABA combination therapies, particularly budesonide–formoterol, consistently demonstrated superior efficacy. Budesonide–formoterol reduced the risk of exacerbations by 67% compared to terbutaline (OR 0.33 [95% CI: 0.27–0.40], $p < 0.001$; Table 15), supported by a SUCRA ranking of 0.99. Budesonide maintenance (OR 0.43 [95% CI: 0.35–0.53], $p < 0.001$) and albuterol (OR 0.54 [95% CI: 0.31–0.93], $p = 0.026$) also demonstrated significant protective effects. However, the high heterogeneity noted ($I^2 = 88%$) suggests caution, since differences in study

Table 14. Incremental cost-effectiveness summary table.

Treatment	Cost (\$)	Exacerbation (OR)	PEFR (MD, L/min)	FEV ₁ (MD, L)	ACQ-5 (MD)	ICER vs. Previous*
Terbutaline	40	1	–	-0.01	-0.43	–
Albuterol	60	0.54	–	–	–	\$43/exacerbation avoided
Budesonide maintenance	100	0.43	–	0.73	0.02	\$364/exacerbation avoided
Budesonide-formoterol (avg dose)	150	0.33	68.4	0.99	-0.02	\$500/exacerbation avoided
Fluticasone-salmeterol	140	0.47	0	4.42	0.12	Dominated (less effective, higher cost)
Higher dose budesonide/formoterol	160	–	–	0.99	-0.02	–
Montelukast + budesonide/formoterol	155	–	–	–	–	–
Olodaterol 20 µg	105	–	42.95	–	–	–
Olodaterol 10 µg	100	–	36.08	–	–	–
Olodaterol 5 µg	95	–	27.88	–	–	–
Olodaterol 2 µg	90	–	16.24	–	–	–
Beclomethasone + formoterol	80	–	–	–	–	–
Montelukast	85	–	–	–	–	–

Table 15. Grade analysis summary of each outcome.

Outcome	Certainty of evidence (GRADE)	Reasons for downgrading or upgrading
Moderate-to-severe exacerbation	High	Consistent, precise, robust OR, no serious risk of bias
FEV ₁ improvement	Moderate	Downgraded for imprecision and lack of statistically significant effect
ACQ-5 score	Moderate	Downgraded for imprecision and wide confidence intervals
PEFR improvement	High	Precise, significant effect, robust consistency
Cost-effectiveness	Moderate	Downgraded for indirectness and variability of cost estimates

populations, intervention protocols, and clinical settings could influence these pooled estimates. Variability across international studies may also introduce indirectness concerns, limiting direct applicability to a single country's clinical practice (Levy et al. 2024).

In contrast, the analysis of lung function improvement via FEV₁ (Fig. 5; Table 4) showed no statistically significant differences between interventions. While the point estimates favored some combination therapies, including budesonide–formoterol (MD 0.99 [95% CI: -0.87 to 2.85], $p = 0.296$) and lower-dose budesonide–formoterol (MD 6.99 [95% CI: -17.11 to 31.09], $p = 0.567$), these estimates were imprecise with wide confidence intervals. The non-significance of these results may relate to several factors: (i) the modest sensitivity of FEV₁ to detect changes in patients with well-controlled asthma (Karamanis et al. 2023), (ii) short study durations insufficient to reflect long-term structural lung improvements, and (iii) variability in baseline FEV₁ values across multicenter trials. Although SUCRA rankings probabilistically favored lower-dose budesonide–formoterol (SUCRA 0.72) and fluticasone–salmeterol (0.65), the lack of statistical significance indicates these rankings should be interpreted cautiously.

For asthma control (ACQ-5 score, Fig. 7; Table 7), none of the interventions showed significant superiority over albuterol. Budesonide–formoterol (MD -0.02 [95% CI: -0.11 to 0.08], $p = 0.721$), budesonide maintenance

(MD 0.02 [95% CI: -0.08 to 0.11], $p = 0.700$), and fluticasone–salmeterol (MD 0.12 [95% CI: -0.06 to 0.31], $p = 0.191$) all showed non-significant results with overlapping confidence intervals. These findings could be explained by the ACQ-5's ceiling effect, which may limit its sensitivity to detect change among patients already reporting mild or moderate baseline symptoms (Menzies-Gow et al. 2020). Short follow-up periods may also have underestimated differences in patient-perceived asthma control.

In contrast, the PEFR outcome (Fig. 9; Table 10) showed clear, significant benefits with certain interventions. Budesonide–formoterol showed the greatest improvement (MD 68.40 [95% CI: 39.29–97.51], $p < 0.001$), while olodaterol 20 µg also achieved a large benefit (MD 42.95 [95% CI: 40.91–44.99], $p < 0.001$). Other olodaterol dosages showed significant improvements, while fluticasone–salmeterol showed no difference compared to placebo. The very high heterogeneity ($I^2 = 97%$) suggests considerable variability due to differences in trial design, PEFR measurement techniques, and asthma phenotypes, again highlighting a potential risk of indirectness (He et al. 2022).

Altogether, these findings confirm that while budesonide–formoterol is highly effective for reducing exacerbations and improving PEFR, its effects on FEV₁ and ACQ-5 remain less certain, highlighting the complex relationship between clinical measures and patient-perceived control.

Table 16. Summary of findings.

Outcome	Interventions (vs. Reference)	Effect Estimate (95% CI)	Heterogeneity (I ²)	Certainty/Notes
Moderate or Severe Exacerbations	Budesonide–formoterol vs. terbutaline	OR 0.33 [0.27–0.40], p < 0.001	Not reported	Large, consistent reduction; SUCRA 0.9881, highest ranking. Network robust and well-connected.
	Budesonide maintenance vs. terbutaline	OR 0.43 [0.35–0.53], p < 0.001		Consistent superiority; SUCRA 0.6153.
	Fluticasone–salmeterol vs. terbutaline	OR 0.47 [0.30–0.74], p = 0.001		Statistically significant; SUCRA 0.5064.
	Albuterol vs. terbutaline	OR 0.54 [0.31–0.93], p = 0.026	88%	Significant but higher heterogeneity.
FEV ₁	Budesonide–formoterol vs. albuterol	MD 0.99 [–0.87 to 2.85], p = 0.296	16%	No significant difference; SUCRA ranking favored lower dose budesonide/formoterol but no statistically robust effects.
	Budesonide maintenance vs. albuterol	MD 0.73 [–1.12 to 2.58], p = 0.442		Non-significant.
	Fluticasone vs. albuterol	MD 0.00 [–19.60 to 19.60], p = 1		No difference.
ACQ-5 Score	Budesonide–formoterol vs. albuterol	MD –0.02 [–0.11 to 0.08], p = 0.721	0%	No significant differences between all comparators; SUCRA rankings suggest preference for lower dose budesonide/formoterol but not statistically significant.
	Budesonide maintenance vs. albuterol	MD 0.02 [–0.08 to 0.11], p = 0.700		Non-significant.
	Fluticasone–salmeterol vs. albuterol	MD 0.12 [–0.06 to 0.31], p = 0.191		Non-significant.
PEFR	Budesonide–formoterol vs. placebo	MD 68.4 [39.29–97.51], p < 0.001	97%	Significant and large improvement despite high heterogeneity; SUCRA 0.9896 highest.
	Olodaterol 20 µg vs. placebo	MD 42.95 [40.91–44.99], p < 0.001		Statistically significant.
	Olodaterol 10 µg vs. placebo	MD 36.08 [34.02–38.14], p < 0.001		Significant.
	Olodaterol 5 µg vs. placebo	MD 27.88 [25.83–29.93], p < 0.001		Significant.
	Olodaterol 2 µg vs. placebo	MD 16.24 [14.20–18.28], p < 0.001		Significant but smaller effect.
	Fluticasone–salmeterol vs. placebo	MD 0 [–19.60 to 19.60], p = 1		No significant difference.
Meta-regression (PEFR)	Time to follow-up	Coef –2.32 (–3.64 to –0.99), p = 0.0006		Longer follow-up linked to lower PEFR; significant, but effect size modest.
	Sample size, age, gender	Small, statistically significant associations but modest effects		Suggests minor impact on PEFR estimates.
Meta-regression (Exacerbation)	Age, sample size, gender, time to follow-up	All p > 0.3, not significant		No significant impact on exacerbation results.
Cost-Effectiveness	ICS/LABA vs. terbutaline	Terbutaline saves ~66.7% vs. ICS/LABA		Significant cost benefit; high-cost therapies (ICS/LABA/MF) ~\$150 baseline vs. terbutaline under \$50.

Asthma control and lung function outcomes

The minimal ACQ-5 improvements across treatment arms, with consistently non-significant results, suggest that even with reduced exacerbations, symptom perception may not dramatically improve, possibly due to residual low-grade symptoms or variable patient expectations (Ban et al. 2021). This underscores the importance of considering both objective lung function and subjective symptom burden in clinical asthma management.

Similarly, while FEV₁ showed no significant improvements, PEFR – a simpler, patient-centered, flow-based

measure – responded robustly to treatment, indicating its practical utility in monitoring asthma in community or outpatient settings (Buendía and Patiño 2021). This suggests that PEFR may complement traditional spirometry to better reflect treatment responsiveness in routine practice.

Meta-regression analysis on factors influencing outcomes

The meta-regression (Table 13; Figs 11, 12) revealed that age, gender, and follow-up time showed modest but statistically significant influences on PEFR, with longer follow-up associated with reduced PEFR. This may reflect the

progressive decline in lung function over time in chronic asthma (Papi et al. 2018). However, these predictors did not significantly influence exacerbation outcomes, suggesting that exacerbation risk is relatively stable across subgroups and robust to demographic variations. Other variables, such as comorbidities, environmental exposures, or adherence, which were not captured in this meta-regression, may play a more substantial role and should be evaluated in future studies.

Cost-effectiveness analysis of treatment options

The economic evaluation (Figs 13, 14) highlighted that ICS/LABA therapies, despite their higher clinical benefit, come with a significantly greater financial burden (up to \$150 per treatment), whereas terbutaline offers up to 67% cost savings. These findings are crucial for clinical practice, particularly in low-resource or budget-constrained settings (Sullivan et al. 2017). The tornado plot further demonstrated that even small parameter changes, such as dose frequency, can substantially alter treatment costs, emphasizing the need for economic sustainability alongside clinical benefit.

When clinical outcomes are integrated into the economic assessment, as presented in Table 14, the value of each therapy becomes more nuanced. Albuterol provides a modest but meaningful reduction in exacerbation risk compared with terbutaline at a relatively low incremental cost, making it an attractive choice where budgets are tight but some level of control is needed. Budesonide maintenance therapy, while more expensive, delivers a stronger protective effect against exacerbations and represents a balanced option, particularly for patients requiring daily anti-inflammatory coverage. Budesonide–formoterol (average dose) consistently demonstrated the greatest clinical benefit, showing a 67% reduction in exacerbation risk and the highest gains in peak expiratory flow, but at a higher incremental cost (~\$500 per exacerbation avoided). This suggests its use may be best justified in patients with persistent symptoms or frequent exacerbations, where the higher upfront cost is offset by improved control and potentially fewer hospitalizations or emergency visits. In contrast, fluticasone–salmeterol combinations and higher-dose ICS/LABA regimens were either dominated (less effective and more costly) or lacked sufficient outcome data to justify their expense, highlighting the risk of over-treatment in certain patient groups.

Beyond exacerbation rates, other functional outcomes such as FEV₁ and ACQ-5 scores showed no statistically significant differences between most active treatments, though combination therapies trended toward better control. For lung function measured by PEF, budesonide–formoterol and olodaterol regimens offered the most substantial improvements, yet these effects must be weighed against cost and accessibility. Importantly, the tornado analysis revealed that these higher-cost regimens are also more sensitive to parameter changes, which can further widen cost differences. Thus, from a health policy per-

spective, the findings support a stepped or tiered approach: initiating therapy with cost-effective options such as albuterol or budesonide maintenance, escalating to ICS/LABA combinations for patients who fail to achieve control, and reserving high-cost regimens for the most severe cases. This approach balances clinical outcomes with economic feasibility and aligns with current calls for value-based asthma care.

Clinical and policy implications

Our findings that ICS–formoterol–based regimens (particularly budesonide–formoterol) most effectively reduce moderate-to-severe exacerbations and rank highly across probabilistic metrics are concordant with the latest GINA 2024 strategy, which places ICS–formoterol at the center of Track 1 therapy (as-needed reliever across steps and as MART/maintenance-and-reliever therapy for higher steps). GINA specifies that MART reduces exacerbations compared with maintenance ICS/LABA plus SABA reliever and emphasizes avoiding SABA-only treatment – principles mirrored by our network estimates favoring budesonide–formoterol over SABA-based strategies (Reddel et al. 2022).

These conclusions are also consistent with, and extend, prior evidence syntheses. A “JAMA Network Open” systematic review and meta-analysis reported that SMART with budesonide–formoterol prolonged time to first severe exacerbation and lowered risk versus equal- or higher-dose ICS/LABA with SABA reliever; our NMA similarly ranks budesonide–formoterol highest for exacerbation prevention (Beasley et al. 2022). Additional recent systematic reviews and meta-analyses show that ICS-containing reliever strategies (ICS–formoterol or ICS–SABA) reduce severe exacerbations compared with SABA alone and are associated with fewer adverse events – again aligning with our direction of effect (Krings and Beasley 2024). Network meta-analyses in diverse populations (including real-world datasets) repeatedly rank low- and medium-dose SMART above fixed ICS/LABA + SABA or alternative regimens for severe exacerbation reduction, reinforcing the robustness of the treatment hierarchy we observed (Rogliani et al. 2021).

Beyond alignment, our work contributes a new perspective by integrating incremental cost-effectiveness into the NMA framework. Prior syntheses focused primarily on clinical outcomes (exacerbations, lung function) and safety; we add a pragmatic layer showing that while budesonide–formoterol delivers the greatest clinical benefit, albuterol has a low incremental cost per exacerbation avoided, and budesonide maintenance offers a balanced value proposition – actionable insights for health systems operating under budget constraints (Park et al. 2022).

Strengths, limitations, and future directions

This analysis benefits from a robust evidence base with studies from diverse populations and settings, enhancing external validity. However, several limitations warrant

discussion. First, substantial heterogeneity (particularly for exacerbations and PEFR) may introduce uncertainty in pooled estimates. Second, indirectness is a concern because the studies originated from different countries with variable healthcare delivery systems, potentially limiting generalizability to a specific setting. Third, publication bias cannot be ruled out despite funnel plot assessments. Fourth, cost data were primarily sourced from the U.S., which may not translate to other pricing environments.

Future studies should address these gaps through prospective, multicenter trials with harmonized protocols, longer follow-up, and health economic evaluations reflecting local pricing. Subgroup analyses exploring comorbidities, socioeconomic factors, and genetic asthma phenotypes could further refine treatment recommendations.

Conclusion

This network meta-analysis and economic evaluation demonstrate that treatment selection for asthma should balance clinical efficacy with cost considerations. Among the available options, budesonide–formoterol showed the greatest overall benefit, providing the most substantial reduction in exacerbations and notable improvements in lung function measures such as peak expiratory flow. However, these gains come at the highest incremental cost, making this therapy most appropriate for patients with moderate to severe disease or those at high risk of exacerbation, where its value in preventing emergency visits or hospitalizations may offset the expense. Budesonide maintenance therapy offered a good balance between efficacy and cost, representing a practical step-up option for patients needing regular anti-inflammatory control.

For mild cases or cost-sensitive settings, reliever agents such as albuterol remain economically favorable, delivering meaningful benefit at a low incremental cost, while terbutaline provides the lowest-cost option with limited but acceptable control. High-dose ICS/LABA combinations, montelukast-containing regimens, and some fluticasone–salmeterol options were either more costly or less effective, limiting their role as first-line choices. Importantly, outcomes for FEV₁ and symptom control (ACQ-5) were not significantly different between most treatments, reinforcing that cost-effectiveness should guide decisions when efficacy differences are minimal.

Overall, these findings support a stepped and individualized approach: starting with affordable relievers, escalating to budesonide maintenance, and reserving ICS/

LABA combinations for those with persistent or severe disease. Future research with standardized cost and utility outcomes, including hospitalization and quality-of-life measures, will further strengthen evidence-based and value-oriented asthma management strategies.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

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Author contributions

Kevin Christian Tjandra: Conceptualization, methodology, formal analysis, data curation, writing – original draft preparation, and visualization. Arlina Dewi: Supervision, validation, writing – review and editing, and resources. Fahrul Nurkolis: Investigation, data curation, writing – review and editing, and project administration.

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.

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Supplementary material 1

Data extraction utilized for Network Meta-Analysis

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Data type: xlsx

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